

The Impacts of Reformation and the Challenges of Ecumenism on the Christian Church in Benue State in the Era of Digital Economy

Dr. Franca Shiminenge Jando

Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi

Clement Mdondoorga Ugoh

Post Graduate Student, Department of Religion and Cultural Studies, Benue State University, Makurdi

Abstract

Reformation is one of the major events that restructured the practice of Christianity in Nigeria and the world in general. Its' positive role in reviving and reforming the Christian Church in the era of digital economy is indeed an indispensable development which its impact has endured till the present day. In Benue State like other parts of the globe, the proliferation of Churches with different ideologies, structures, doctrines and teachings in the name of reformation have affected the ecumenical practice. Using qualitative approach, the study adopted historical, descriptive and analytic methods and examined the positive and negative impacts of reformation on the contemporary Church and how the negative impacts have affected the ecumenical practice in Benue state. The study relied on primary and secondary sources of data collection. It is found in the study that, reformation had enormous impacts on the growth and development of modern Church through a variety of causal channels. It led to evangelisation and revival that had made planting of the Church in Benue State and Nigeria possible. It has brought modern liberalism that is experienced among the Christendom in Benue and beyond. The study also found out that, proliferation of Churches and lack of unity which is traceable to the present form of reformation is a key factor that hindered the unity and proper development of the Church which the contemporary Church need to guard against. The study recommended that, the Church needs to checkmate those immoderations of reformation that are brining unnecessary division and proliferation of Churches in Benue State today. The present government of Rev. Fr. Alia through CAN should properly help to check and regulate all these excesses doctrinal practices that are dividing the Christian Church today rather than uniting it for the peace and development of the State and Nigeria at large.

Keywords: Christian Church, Challenges, Reformation, Ecumenism and Development

Introduction

One of the major developments that have taken place in the history of Christianity is the reformation of the 16th century. This event has made a profound impact on the history and the development of the Christendom, its impact is felt even in the contemporary Church. Before the reformation of the 16th century, Christianity was united but due to the perceived abuses within the Christendom, it was not only possible but necessary that, the Church needed a reformation. Reformation is one of the major events that reshaped the practice of Christianity. Its' positive role in reviving and reforming the church is indeed an important development which its impact has endured till the present day. However, reformation has not only helped the Church to reawaken from it slumber but has also planted a seed of division that is rearing its ugly head in the contemporary church. Different churches are emerging on daily basis some of which are with the view of correcting the inadequacies of the old ones. This has the tendency to create proliferation and division in the Christendom.

In Benue State like other parts of the country, new churches coming up with new structures and teaching in the spirit or name of reformation. However, the problem of the study is to appraise the impact reformation has on the contemporary Church. To discuss the positive aspects of the reformation as well as the negative impacts

and to assess the excessive of the reformation in the contemporary church in Benue State. This is what the study set out to investigate.

The Concept of Ecumenism

Ecumenism according to Ibebuike in the broadest sense means the unity across the three Abrahamic faiths of Judaism, Christianity, and Islam. In a narrower sense, it means a greater co-operation among different religious denominations of a particular or single faith. The writer also states that the Roman Catholics, Eastern Orthodox, Anglicans, and other Protestant Churches now engage together in ecumenism in order to promote unity in Christendom through ecumenical dialogues, debates, and academic lectures, social and spiritual activities. He however, mentions that some traditionalist Christian groups such as the traditional Roman Catholics, traditional Orthodox Christians, and the Evangelical Protestants are opposed to ecumenism.¹

Reformation in the Christian Church

The Reformation in the Christian Church is the movement in history, beginning in 1517, which broke up the institutional unity of the Church in Western Europe and established the second great branch of Christianity, called Protestantism, which was and is centered on the absolute and sufficient authority of the bible and on justification by faith alone. This term refers to the leaders of the revolt against Catholicism. Luther, Zwingli, Calvin, Knox, Bucer, Cranmer, and others would merit this title, as would Anabaptists such as Menno Simons.² The religious revolution that took place in the Western Church in the 16th century has its greatest leaders undoubtedly were Martin Luther and John Calvin. Having far-reaching political, economic, and social effects, the Reformation became the basis for the founding of Protestantism, one of the major branches of Christianity.³ The world of the late medieval Roman Catholic Church from which the 16th-century reformers emerged was a complex one. Over the centuries the church, particularly in the office of the papacy, had become deeply involved in the political life of Western Europe.

The resulting intrigues and political manipulations, combined with the church's increasing power and wealth, contributed to the bankrupting of the Church as a spiritual force. Abuses such as the sale of indulgences (or spiritual privileges) by the clergy and other charges of corruption undermined the Church's spiritual authority. These instances must be seen as exceptions, however, no matter how much they were played up by polemicists. For most people, the church continued to offer spiritual comfort. There is some evidence of anticlericalism, but the church at large enjoyed loyalty as it had before. One development is clear: the political authorities increasingly sought to curtail the public role of the church and thereby triggered tension.⁴

Martin Luther claimed that what distinguished him from previous reformers was that while they attacked corruption in the life of the Church, he went to the theological root of the problem the perversion of the church's doctrine of redemption and grace. Luther deplored the entanglement of God's free gift of grace in a complex system of indulgences and good works. In his Ninety-five Theses, he attacked the indulgence system, insisting that the pope had no authority over purgatory and that the doctrine of the merits of the saints had no foundation in the gospel. Here lay the key to Luther's concerns for the ethical and theological reform of the church: Scripture alone is authoritative (*Sola scriptura*) and justification is by faith (*Sola fidei*), not by works. While he did not intend to break with the Catholic Church, a confrontation with the papacy was not long in coming in 1521 Luther was excommunicated; what began as an internal reform movement had become a fracture in western Christendom.⁵

The Reformation movement within Germany diversified almost immediately, and other reform impulses arose independently of Luther. Huldrych Zwingli built a Christian theocracy in Zurich in which church and state joined for the service of God. Zwingli agreed with Luther in the centrality of the doctrine of justification by faith, but he espoused a different understanding of the Holy Communion. Luther had rejected the Catholic Church's doctrine of transubstantiation, according to which the bread and wine in Holy Communion became the actual body and blood of Christ. According to Luther's notion, the body of Christ was physically present in the elements

because Christ is present everywhere, while Zwingli claimed that entailed a spiritual presence of Christ and a declaration of faith by the recipients.⁶ Another group of reformers, often though not altogether correctly referred to as “radical reformers,” insisted that baptism be performed not on infants but on adults who had professed their faith in Jesus.⁷

Another important forms of Protestantism (as those protesting against their suppressions were designated by the Diet of Speyer in 1529) as Calvinism, named for John Calvin, a French lawyer who fled France after his conversion to the Protestant cause. In Basel, Switzerland, Calvin brought out the first edition of his Institutes of the Christian religion in 1536, the first systematic, theological treatise of the new reform movement. Calvin agreed with Luther’s teaching on justification by faith. However, he found a more positive place for law within the Christian community than did Luther. In Geneva, Calvin was able to experiment with his ideal of a disciplined community of the elect. Calvin also stressed the doctrine of predestination and interpreted Holy Communion as a spiritual partaking of the body and blood and Christ. Calvin’s tradition merged eventually with Zwingli’s into the Reformed tradition, which was given theological expression by the (second) Helvetic Confession of 1561.⁸

The Reformation spread to other European countries over the course of the 16th century. By mid-century, Lutheranism dominated northern Europe. Eastern Europe offered a seedbed for even more radical varieties of Protestantism, because kings were weak, nobles strong, and cities few, and because religious pluralism had long existed. Spain and Italy were to be the great centres of the Catholic Counter-Reformation, and Protestantism never gained a strong foothold there.⁹ In England the reformation’s roots were both political and religious. Henry VII incensed by Pope Clement VII’s refusal to grant him an annulment of his marriage, repudiated papal authority and in 1534 established the Anglican Church with the king as the supreme head. In spite of its political implications, the re-organisation of the Church permitted the beginning of religious change in England, which included the preparation of a liturgy in English, the Book of Common Prayer. In Scotland, John Knox, who spent time in Geneva and was greatly influenced by John Calvin, led the establishment of Presbyterianism, which made possible the eventual union of Scotland with England.¹⁰

The State of the Church before the Reformation

The middle Ages are by no means the “dark ages.” Many achievements of the medieval church are to be admired and adopted. Anselm, for instance, began to teach the first clearly acceptable doctrine of the atonement in 1099. On the other hand, Anselm was one of the most extreme admirers of Mary, and was influential to increase Marian devotion.¹¹ The monastic movement had how been a powerful influence for over 1000 years. The monks and nuns preserved for all time a vision of devotion to God and personal relationship with him which has become instructive to all believers. Yet, this was in a context of vows and celibacy that was artificial and not related to everyday human life. The medieval Church didn’t really believe that everyday believers would or could have this kind of life with God.¹² There was no clear indication that a crisis was approaching, or that current efforts to reform the Church from within could not continue peacefully.

At the beginning of the sixteenth century, Europeans were questioning old values and forms. The masses reacted to priestly authority as never before. Most priests were immoral, corrupt, or illiterate knowing just enough Latin to celebrate the mass by rote memory. Renaissance humanism influenced most of Europe. The renaissance de-emphasised “universals” placing a greater emphasis on “particulars.” The attention paid the individual and his ability to think reason independently illustrates the emphasis on particulars. Learned men accepted the twin concepts of human ability and intellect Carrington.¹³

Even as thinkers questioned values and forms, there was an accompanying revival of religious feeling. The Brethren of the Common Life accomplished this among mainstream Catholics. They stressed mystical experience and subjectivism. Most people had grown weary of empty formalism and sought meaning, along with practical application, in their religious experience.¹⁴ When the reformation began, it touched everything. It even left an indelible mark on culture. Historian insists modern Germany would not be Germany were it not for Martin Luther. The reformation affected political institutions, particularly Calvinism with its emphasis vocation and the

separation of Church and state. The reformation called medieval scholastics to task, thus shaping theology. Reformers made the Bible family life became a model for all German protestant families.¹⁵ On the one hand, Reformers saw themselves as saviors of Europe and Europe's religion. They removed much of Europe from papal tyranny and brought to it Christ's authority. Where Protestantism predominated, Catholic financial exploitation departed. On the other hand, Catholics believe all infidelity began with the reformation. Catholics portray Luther as a drunken monk and his home life as debauchery.¹⁶

The reformation did not reform religion. Instead, it reformed institutions. Alexander Campbell correctly wrote:

All the famous reformations in history have rather been reformations of creeds and clergy, than of religion. Since the New Testament was finished, it is fairly to be presumed that there cannot be any reformation of religion, properly so called. Though called reformations of religion, they have always left religion where it was. I do not think that King Harry (Sic) was a white more religion when he proclaimed himself head of the Church of England, than when writing against Luther on the seven sacraments, as a true son of the Church of Rome. It is even questionable whether Luther himself, the elector of Saxony, the Marquis of Brandenburg, the Duke of Lunenburg, the Landgrave of Hesse, and the Prince of Anhalt, were more religious men when they signed the Augsburg Confession of Faith than when they formerly repeated their Ave Maria.¹⁷

Human creeds may be reformed and re-reformed, and be erroneous still, like their authors; but the inspired creeds needs no reformation, being like its author, infallible. The clergy too may be reformed from papistical opinions, grimaces, tricks, and dresses, to protestant opinions and ceremonies; protestant clergy may be reformed from protestant to Presbyterian metaphysics and forms; and Presbyterian clergy may be reformed to independency, and yet the Pope remains in their heart. They are clergy still-and-still in need of reformation.¹⁸

There are different Christian denominations in Benue State even though, the first to come were the NKST followed Roman Catholic Church. Today, there are numerous Pentecostal Churches apart from these mainline Churches. Benue State like other states of the federation is witnessing a rapid expansion of Pentecostal Churches even though these Churches were not the earliest ones planted by the missionaries, there is indeed a significant growth and impact on these churches in Benue state and Makurdi Metropolis to be specific. The history of these Churches revealed that, their advent in Benue state and Makurdi was well after the arrival of mainline Churches; NKST (URCC) and Roman Catholic Church. However, Pentecostal Churches have enjoyed rapid expansion in Benue state and Makurdi which is the state capital have quite a good number of Pentecostal Churches. While NKST (URCC) and Roman Catholic Church have covered the vast areas in Benue State especially the rural areas, Pentecostal Churches have made a significant impact in mostly urban and semi urban areas in the state. The state has a larger population of Christians and there are Christian churches all over the state.

The Impact of Reformation on the Christian Churches in Benue State in the Era of Digital Economy

Reformation has brought a number of positive changes that we can still see in the contemporary Church in Benue State. Some of the impacts could be seen in the introduction and planting of the gospel in Benue State, abolition of the killing of twins, the wide use of the Bible, improvement on healthcare delivery, Western education, political and social awareness among other things.

1. The Use of the Bible: As earlier stated, reformation has reawakened a general desire and love for the Bible as the written word of God, and as a perennial document of authentic Christian moral life, Many Christians are nowadays taking the bible seriously and it is no longer consider as a book meant for the clergy. The translation and mass printing of the Bible was possible because of the impact of reformation.

2. The Planting of the Gospel in Benue State: The planting of the Church in Benue state like other parts of the world was made possible because of reformation. This is because, after the reformation, the revival that was experienced brought about a number of missionary societies that evangelise different parts of the world including Benue state. This has made it possible for the state to receive the gospel of salvation and today we have many

Churches in the state. This has afforded the people of the state to have salvation at their door step. Following Martin Luther's protest against Catholic Church in 1517 which led to the birth of the protestant Church out of the Catholic Church, John Churches emanated; (a) the Presbyterians Churches (b) the Reformed Churches were established in Holland and South Africa is the discourse in focus, the Church (URCC) was a creation of the Dutch Reformed Church mission (DRCM). It became operational in Tiv land in 1911, Benue State.

History has it that, there were group of protestant that met in England in 1902, they prayed for the success of the gospel work in Africa with particular attention to the Sudan region, Dr. Karl Kumn and his wife Lucy Kumn were part of this prayer group and had been to the Sudan region in Africa, appealed that missionaries should be sent to Sudan in order to check the Muslim and prevent them from taking control of the place, a follow up group was formed at the meeting known as Sudan Pioneer Mission (SPM) in 13th November, 1902.¹⁹ This action brought about motivation in the side of other protestant churches in support of the missionaries work in Sudan.

In 1904 they met in Edinburg in England where they suggested new name came, Sudan United Mission (SUM) this was because it was not only one Church to be involved, the unity of different Churches has to be emphasised, these missionaries arrived in Nigeria at Lokoja on August, 10th 1904, it was this very year that the Tiv nation also hosted the SUM) team. In the year 1907, Dr. Karl Kumn who led the delegation, went to south Africa and asked the Dutch Reformed Church to come and evangelise the Tiv Nation, this request was granted and in 1908, missionaries were sent in the Tiv area, they arrived Nigeria and had access to the Tiv people on April 7th 1911 in a village called Sai in Katsina-Ala local government area of Benue State.²⁰

3. Abolition of the Killing of Twins: If not for the Christian missionaries, twins were killed because of negative cultural practices. But with the coming of the missionaries and the enlightenment they brought, people no longer look at twine as something evil. This is another reason one can appreciate the impact of reformation in the State.

4. Improved Healthcare Delivery: The missionaries from different denomination made positive contributions to Benue state and Tiv in particular in religion, education, healthcare, agriculture and social wellbeing. The missionaries also took care of the health needs of the people to enhance their wellbeing. In line with providing health care for the people, the missionaries established many hospitals, clinics and maternity homes, by NKST, Catholic Church and other Churches. They include St. Elizabeth Hospital, Vandeikya, St. Vincent Hospital, Aliade, St, Monica Adikpo, Bishop Murray Medical Centre, Makurdi and the NKST Rehabilitation Hospital at Mkar also teaches handiwork for the lepers in camp, so that they can be useful to themselves and the society at large.²¹

5. Religious Impact: With the coming of Christianity in Benue state, some religious reforms took place, for instance, the worship of idols and belief in witchcraft activities reduced in Tiv drastically. The beliefs in Ibovungu in Tivland, Alekwu cult in Idoma and Achukwu in Igede had declined. Polygamy that was the culture of the Benue people has also declined and monogamy seems to have gained more ground. Some religious negative taboos among the Tiv, idoma and Igede people have been exterminated. For example, twins and the mal-formed children were killed among people in Benue state. All the immoral practices or acts against humanity have reduced because of Christianity.²²

6. Educational Impact: The Christian Churches especially the Catholic Church and the URCC have established schools wherever they are found. This is order to bring education to the people's doorstep. Missionaries as a process of religious and moral character training presented education. The education obtained has really broadened the horizons of the people. The gospel message has been translated into the different native languages of Benue; Tiv, Idoma and Igede and so on, with Christian songs, simple prayer and catechism.

According to Denga, Tiv traditional education was based on oral tradition and practical activities focused on domestic life and occupations such as cooking, child-rearing, farming and manufacturing of clothes. Missionaries introduced western education and maintained the wide-gap lead throughout the sixty years of British colonial rule in Tiv land (January 1900-October 1960).²³ Tiv traditional education was altogether informal education without special school premises, classrooms, employed teachers with salaries, books exercise books,

pens, pencils, erasers, chalk or white board markers, black boards and boarding facilities. Contradistinction, western education was a formal education and had school premises, classrooms, employed teachers with salaries, inspectors, books and stationeries, among other things.²⁴

This was made possible by the effort of the Missionaries and NKST Church has continued carry out this important task of educating people through her various institutions. There was a system of writing accompanied by English language, Western education transformed traditional education and the entire Tiv society in terms of knowledge, skills and activities? Tiv language was in an oral form, but not in a written form. All forms of communication were done by speech. Tiv conversation, discussion and messages were all carried out though spoken Tiv. They did not have any system of alphabet or a set of letters that could be used to write Tiv language. DRCM introduced English letters into Tiv language and made Tiv language a written language.²⁵

The English letters were as follows: A B C D E F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z . These letters were given Tiv names and they were used in writing Tiv language. As a result, the Holy Bible (*Chian Bibilo*) hymns (*atsam*), catechism (*katekisem*) and books were translated into Tiv and used in Churches (*ayou aduaa*) and schools (*imakarenta*). Missionaries introduced also Arabic umbers: 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 and Roman numbers: i ii iii iv v vi vii viii ix x into Tiv language.²⁶ Numbers were used in mathematics or arithmetic's and pagination of published works or books, the Holy Bible catechism, minutes and manuscripts. The introduction of numbers contributed significantly to the development of both oral and written forms of Tiv language.

7. Agricultural Impact: The Christian denominations that brought the gospel believed in politic wellbeing; therefore they established agricultural projects in the state. For example, the NKST HAS a concentration of its agricultural projects at Mkar, while the Catholics established theirs at Abwa-Mbagen. They provided improved seeds and seedlings and farming implements such as tractors and insecticides to the people.

8. Social and Political Impact: DRCM missionaries taught the Tiv that all men and women were equal before God (Aondo). The equality of the human race and individuals is held in the Holy Bible on grounds that all human beings were created by one and the same God, or evolved from unnamed one living cell for those who reject the whole idea of God. Among human qualities, all human beings have the same type of life that dies away at a point in time.²⁷ All human beings feel hungry, thirst, hot, cold, angry, pain and comfort. They all have faculties of knowing, thinking, reasoning, deciding, choosing and exercising freewill. They all have moral autonomy and consent in addition to biological similarities. In politics, the equality of persons is embedded in the principles of the rule of law or equality before the law and the poser of one person, one vote.

Christian missionaries taught the Tiv Christians that all human beings or all ethnic groups were equal before God. Colonial officials discouraged this doctrine because it would make the people think that they and Europeans were equal. Colonial rulers feared that the doctrine of the equality of persons could damage the 99-year plan of colonial rule in Northern Nigeria. Christian missionaries went ahead and taught what the Holy Bible says. Thus, this important political idea or principle was inculcated in Tiv land through teaching, sermon, hymns and catechism, political education was inculcated through Church and ministration.

Christian missionaries brought to Tivland the first and the best political textbook whit valuable and lasting political facts and ideas. We are talking about the Hoy Bible. It talks about political and social history of the people of Israel in relation to those political and social histories of other nations such as Egypt, Canaan and Bbylonia. It talks about how instability brought forth responsible leaders such as Joseph, Moses, Joshua and Deborah. Challenges of international conflict caused a political change from theocracy with limited powers to make ultimate decisions and to take decisive actions.²⁸ The Holy Bible shows how inordinate political ambition led King Saul to become jealously and wickedly violent against his so-in-law called David. Saul went to war against the Philistines and commanded he army personally.

He eventually got killed in war with his heir. Many of his men perished in that war. This brief analysis has revealed basic political facts, ideas and styles of political behavior and conflict. Apart from the moral, spiritual and social development, the NKST Church is contributing immensely in the physical development of the land through infrastructural development, business and economic activities and other diverse way that are transforming

the Tiv nation. The NKST planted plenty of mango, orange and guava trees in all mission stations across Tivland. The early mission stations were Saai, Aki Biam, Mkar, Adikpo, Mbaakon, Jato Aku, Aku, Ikyaaava, Apir, Abwa, Makurdi, among several others.

Through mission stations, the practice of fruit production was cultivated among the Tiv. Along with fruit production, there was cultivation of vegetables. Thus, the production of fruits and vegetables expanded agriculture and enriched general nutrition of the Tiv. The Church made a contribution to the promotion of modern business through road construction, building of stations, electrification of mission stations, pipe water supply, wholesale and retail marketing of books and stationeries, printing press, maintenance workshops and carpentry.²⁹ Through these commercial activities, missionaries inculcated business ideas, skills, practice and orientation among church members, the concepts of business, trade, wholesale, retail, marketing, profit and loss, 'purchase and supply, enterprise, entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial leadership and business management were all embedded in the programmes of the Church in Benue state. These were part and parcel of daily missionary activities in Church and society.

In order to build residential houses, administrative and business workshops, the missionaries imported building materials such as iron rods, roofing sheets, nails, hammers, locks and keys, among other building materials. Books, stationeries, hymns and Bibles were imported and sold to local traders in Church and society. The missionaries engaged in business enterprises in order that the local Church being instituted should enjoy self-governing, self-extension or self-propagating, self-supporting and independent. These principles of Church planting were put forward by Henry Venn who was one of the early Nigerian Church founders, including Thomas Birch Freeman, Samuel Ajayi Crowther, Henry Townsend and T.B. Macaulay. The local Church was to be a national institution fit for a local culture.³⁰ NKST Church took over this gesture from the Missionaries and are carrying out physical developments in different parts of the country.

These various areas have shown the efforts of the Church in the physical, social, spiritual, economic and educational development in Tiv land. These various instances are a clear manifestation of the fact that, the church as a social institution in the society must be committed to the promotion of social justice in the society in which it found itself. The word peace remains a recurring decimal in the Church. Soon after the resurrection, the first blessing that Christ gave his church was that of peace: Peace be with you, the church has in consonance with this event, preached and sought peace all over the world, and especially in the family which is the basis of national and world peace, in the community, in the country and the world. In its involvement in the search for peace for the nation, the Christian Church has been preaching unity and reconciliation. The Church provides education to the teaming youths and gives scholarship grants to youths that are members of the Church as well as orphans who lacked educational opportunities with the view of empowering them and making them self-reliant.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study has examined the impact of reformation on the contemporary Church in Benue state. The protestant reformation was indeed one of the most consequential events in modern history, and it is important to take stock on how it has affected the growth and the development of the Church in the present era. There have been prolonged discussions about the reformation's impact on a variety of phenomena linked to modernity, but there are three that are of particular importance found in the study. The first concerns the Reformation's impact on the development modern states. The second has to do with the Lutheran Reformation's role in shaping the modern concept of identity. The third has to do with Reformation's impact on modern liberalism that is experienced in the Church.

The Reformation had huge impacts on the development of modern states in Europe and African, through a variety of causal channels. It led to evangelisation and revival that had made planting of the church in Nigeria and mostly in Benue State possible. It has brought modern liberalism that is experienced among the Christendom however; the study also found that, proliferation and lack of unity which is traceable to reformation is a factor that is affecting the growth and unity of the contemporary church in Benue State and beyond.

The church in Benue State like the church elsewhere has been affected by the changes brought by the reformation. Reformation has brought a number of positive changes that we can still see in the contemporary church in Benue State. Some of the impact could be seen in the introduction and planting of the gospel in Benue State, abolition of the killing of twins, the wide use of the Bible, improved healthcare delivery, Western education, political and social awareness among other things. Today, the church is more democratic now than before but there is unguided division that must be checked if the church must have unity of purpose.

In the first place, there must be the avoidance of negative traits that often lead to antagonism. According to Iwe, for religion to be ecumenically focused, it must avoid arrogance, fanaticism, discrimination and so on and therefore emphasise the idea of God, one people, one culture and religion.⁴⁰ This means that, regardless of suspicion, skepticism and prejudice among the churches, each group should jettison her personal biases, selfishness and pride and focus more on ways of having a common understanding of the meaning of ecumenism. Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations have been added:

- i. There is need for the contemporary church to guard against the ills that caused reformation of the 16th century
- ii. The church need to check the excesses of reformation like unnecessary division and proliferation of churches that is going on today.
- iii. The church need to regulate and checkmate those doctrinal differences that are dividing the Christianity today.
- iv. The Church in Benue state needs to have unity of purpose for a positive impact and to serve as a social voice to the society to enhance peace and development in Benue State and beyond.

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